

Gender discrimination and choice of decision-making among the Working Women in Kerala

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Abstract: Every human being, regardless of gender, race, language, socio-economic class, origin, discipline, or background, needs to be treated fairly and equitably. All people' rights and duties in the workplace should be equal and consistent at all periods and in every circumstance. Women deserve to be on par with men by virtue of being human. Women constitute almost half of the population, and if they are not treated well the society will not progress and the nation will not develop. Women play many roles in life, after her birth she proves herself to be a daughter, then as a wife and finally as a mother. In the modern era, changes occurred in their life, and women took part in gaining education and job prospects. Despite their involvement in these activities, they made a substantial contribution to the society. The objectives of the study are to know the current status of gender discrimination among the working women and to find out the choice of decision-making among working Women. The methodology of the study adopts descriptive research design for the data collection interview schedule is used which includes both open ended and close ended interview schedule and on both primary and secondary data The study consists of 200 samples selected through a purposive sampling method for the purpose of selecting married working women. The study finding reveals that the existence of pervasive gender discrimination in workplaces, necessitating proactive measures to address issues likes bias, lost opportunities, and gender-related challenges. Furthermore, many working women endorse gender equality principles and receive support from their managers; though translating these beliefs into tangible actions for fostering equitable and inclusive work environments remains a crucial challenge.

Keywords: *Gender Discrimination, Patriarchy, Decision-Making, Working Women*

Introduction

Women work inside and outside home still their work remains unaccounted. Women work to maintain their family, take care for children and elders, they are taking care the health in the family members, still certain decisions does not depend on them because in the traditional

concept they are not considered as bread earner for the family. This traditional concept of division of labour makes women more vulnerable when it is found that they work inside home doing all things and maintaining family and outside home to earn something for the family, and still it remains a fact that women's work is considered lower than male.

Women's unpaid work like household work and care is not taken into account in the economy (Desai, 2015). Because of industrialization and urbanization new social standards were formed and way of living for individuals has changed. Confronted with, financial hardship and dire societal conditions leading women to circumstance where they found it better to look for paid work outside the home. Now a days the percentage of women to leave their houses for work expanded many fold. In the early period women were for the most part occupied with semi-valued occupations, as attendants, cooks, household workers, as agricultural workers. Yet, now they are progressively being utilized in administrations, commercial enterprises, shops, foundations, workplaces what's more, expert/specialized occupations. This change upgraded the status of women from one viewpoint and the condition of the nation also develops by that on the other yet it is found that women are harassed in many ways and are troubled in the work environment became a method to show them their position in the society which as a concept is believed by patriarchy.

Gender Discrimination

The discriminatory act must have been conducted with a discriminating motive, and motive can be deduced from behaviour. Some instances like consider a company that repeatedly hires males from a pool of applicants of both genders, compensation disparities based on gender and when men and women do the same job but advance at different rates. The conduct must be aimed against an individual, and the victim's gender must be shown to be the cause of the discrimination. A boss must treat every job candidate on his or her merits and not stereotype females as incapable of fulfilling the chores that his services entail.

There is indirect discrimination when a requirement is applied to which a significantly smaller percentage of members of a particular gender can comply when compared to the other gender, and such requirement or state is not justifiable regardless of sex, and those to whom it is applied suffers as a result. For an example is the differential in remuneration disbursement based on employee gender, which causes the female employees receiving unequal pay.

Patriarchal System in India

According to Hotelling (1991), certain acts for men and women are culturally acceptable and unacceptable, according to society. The conventional view additionally trusts that working class women should restrict their job chances to particular female employments such as teachers, nurses and secretaries. Thus it is evident that these sorts of mind set and activities are deeply rooted into the society, though many law, rights and acts are coming to protect the dignity of women and give them a proper place in the society still these sorts of mindset and attitude is quite a challenge to change. In these way men believe they have power to dominate women. While discussing gender discrimination Men behave out of strong competitiveness and concern for ego, or out of fear of losing authority. Men do not wish to appear frail or helpless not manly and they do not want other men to discuss it, so they inherit a nature of discussing and assessing women's bodies, squeezing women, making implied or overt threats, or spying on women are all examples of inappropriate behaviour. Both Indian men and women believe that females are the weaker sex- weaker physically, emotionally and in opinion of some, intellectually as well. Most parents do not want girl child because they are considered liabilities. They must be protected, given a dowry and married in a good family (Singh, 2004). This is the existing mindset in the society about women.

Gender Discrimination and Society

When something happens to an employee it is not only the sole responsibility of the person who faced harassment to deal with the problem, it is also the responsibility of the organization to look into the matter and bring a productive solution. It is absolutely necessary to bring equilibrium in the workplace among men and women which would bring peace and justice removing all odds proving to be productive for both the employer and the employee. Though unequal power relationships exist not only in different strata of workplace but also in the society. Economic modernization has brought a change in the family patterns and roles. This change in the mindset is not so much as it is expected but people still engage themselves in different activities which leads to dominance at workplace. Women are having education and gaining confidence which is making them depend less on men as they can go out and earn. Women need security everywhere so that they can establish their identity without any obstacle. Society generally carries an age old conception for women and it's time to change the conception.

Challenges faced by Working Women in India

Working at home and in the workplace is not an easy challenge for women. The issues and difficulties become amplified as a result of the social, biological, and psychological factors, as well as the mass illiteracy and ignorance (Mir, 2003). Women also face many types of problems at home, much of the progress can be seen in science and technology but still the problem and condition remains almost same. The state of women in India in general is thought to be extremely hopeless. In the patriarchal view point work is economically productive and hence women's work at home is not economically assessed as productive and it is considered to be unimportant which is for the consumption of the house hold people (Sankaran, 2006).

However women face many types of problems when they take unpaid work outside home and are paid for it. Not only they face discrepancies at work regarding salary but also they have to deal with many kinds of harassment including sexual harassment which makes them more prone to health hazards and this is the worst thing which can happen to them (Landrine and A.Klonoff, 1997). Many times it is found that women often face restrained but persistent harassment, they are not considered as intelligent as men. It shows lack of respect towards women and they are not treated women equally. This feeling makes women physically and mentally ill. It is very important here to understand discrimination against women and its perception. It has variety of forms such as sexual discrimination, treated unfairly, not believing on them that they could do better by their own aptitude etc. So this paper is focused on the status of women in workplace and the process women go through and how they cope up with the society and how much they have the courage can able to voice up for their rights?

Statement of the problem

Women confront many sorts of inequity in the work environment and also women are misused more than men which make women helpless. Numerous of the circumstances can be found where women are not given any promotions because though they remain in power in terms of qualification but they are made to believe that they cannot go up in relation to any male counterpart. Gender inequality is well felt in the workplaces. And women are frequently

considered as inefficient and not qualified to perform similar way with men. Individuals have a tendency to trust that a woman achievement is because of fortunes or diligent work.

Need of the study

More women are entering workforce these days, so it is important to know the perspective of male population as our society is patriarchal. The outlook of the male population in gender differences will reveal the way in which they think about the other half of inhabitants. This study is important as it is the main root cause of obstruction of awareness among masses and awareness is one of the basic pathways to stop these kinds of social evils.

Methodology

Objectives of the study

- To know the current status of gender discrimination among working women
- To find out the choice of decision-making among working Women

Research design

A very elaborate and descriptive research design has been applied. The study follows quantitative method includes an open-ended and closed-ended interview schedule.

Sampling procedure

Both organized and unorganized sectors women workers were selected for the study.

Universe

Married women who are working in organised and unorganised sector within the age of 20 to 55 years residing in Kerala.

Unit of the study

Purposive sampling procedure which is a type of non- probability sampling was used to gather information from a sample size of 200 respondents.

Sampling technique

A purposive sampling technique procedure is used in this research. Purposive technique mainly depends on the judgment of the researcher.

Tool and Technique for data collection

After selecting the area of the study, developed the sampling frame for the respondents. Keeping in mind the nature of the present study data was collected with the help of an

interview schedule. The In-depth interview was conducted with the help of a structured interview schedule with open-ended questions

Tool used for data analysis

After completing interview schedule data was analyzed with the help of basic statistical tools like Mean, Frequency, Percentage, Standard deviation and other appropriate statistical methods.

Source of data

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data. However, the main focus is on primary sources. The secondary data was collected from various books, magazines, journals, Government organizations, and Internet.

Research Findings

Table: 1, Work profile of working women

A work profile of the working women of Kerala given below in order to understand the sectors of work the sample size of 200 women indicated which sector of work they belonged to:-

Sl. No	Sectors	Frequency	Percentage
1	Teaching profession	88	44
2	Private job	55	27.5
3	Government Service	26	13
4	Corporate service	10	5
5	Business	4	2
6	Unskilled Worker	17	8.5
Total		200	100

The majority (44 per cent) of the women are in teaching sector. Its indicating the significant presence of professionals in the education field and 27.5 per cent of the respondents belongs to private sector, 13 percent of the respondents belong to Government sector, 8.5 per cent of the respondents are unskilled worker, 5 percent of the respondents belong to corporate sector, its indicating the smaller presence of professionals in corporate roles and fewer respondents are self-employed business sector.

Table: 2, Gender Discrimination in the Workplace

A Likert scale is a commonly used tool for data collection, typically consisting of statements or questions to which respondents express their level of agreement or disagreement.

Respondents are presented with a range of response options including "Strongly Disagree," "Disagree," "Neutral," "Agree," and "Strongly Agree," allowing researchers to quantify and analyze people's attitudes, opinions, or perceptions on a particular subject. Here the data explain the gender discrimination and workplace dynamic, along with the mean rating given by the Working Women.

Sl. No	Items	Mean	SD
1	I feel gender discrimination in my workplace?	4.09	1.338
2	I lost a career opportunity due of my gender?	3.47	1.333
3	Do you believe that your gender requires you to work more at your job?	4.51	1.303
4	Do you believe that men were superior to women in work?	3.66	1.440
5	Do you believe that women in your workplace have fewer opportunities than men?	4.03	1.582
6	Do you believe that women could fill a high position at your company?	3.04	1.689
7	Have you ever had to go to desperate measure to get a promotion?	1.46	0.955
8	Do you believe that men receive promotions more than women in your company?	3.33	1.353
9	Do both men and women get paid the same amount of money for the same job at your workplace?	3.47	1.442
10	Do you believe that men and women should be treated as equal in the workplace?	2.45	1.377
11	I receive the respect I deserve from my colleagues	3.01	1.056
12	The management and the manager encouraged me	3.82	1.120

The presented data provides a comprehensive overview of the prevalent gender dynamics and workplace experiences in the Kerala context. It is evident from the data results that gender discrimination is a pressing concern in workplaces, with respondents reporting a substantial perception of bias, lost job opportunities, and the need to exert extra effort due to their gender. The data also highlights the existence of a gender hierarchy and inequalities in opportunities and promotions, as well as concerns about wage disparities between men and women. These findings indicate the persistence of gender-based challenges and biases that impede women's career progression and reinforce the urgency of promoting gender equality in workplaces.

Despite the noted disparities, it is encouraging to see that working women generally support the principle of gender equality and feels relatively encouraged by management and their managers. This suggests a willingness to address these issues and implement positive changes. However, the survey results also indicate a room for improvement in translating these beliefs into concrete actions that lead to more equitable and inclusive work environments. In summary, this data underscores the need for a concerted effort to bridge the gender gap in workplaces, fostering fairer opportunities, promoting equality, and creating a more supportive and inclusive atmosphere for all employees.

Table: 3, I have the liberty to take decision on my family and work matters

Sl. No	Rating	Frequency	Percent
1	Strongly Disagree	10	5.0
2	Disagree	28	14.0
3	Neutral	126	63.0
4	Agree	14	7.0
5	Strongly Agree	22	11.0
Total		200	100.0

The most notable observation is that the majority of respondents fall into the "Neutral" category, representing 63% of the sample, indicating that a significant proportion of individuals did not strongly agree or disagree with the survey statements. While 11% expressed "Strongly Agree" and 7% "Agree," it's important to recognize that a substantial 19% expressed disagreement, with 14% in the "Disagree" category and 5% in "Strongly Disagree." This distribution suggests that the surveyed population has a wide range of views and opinions on Decision-Making, with the most common response being a neutral stance.

Suggestions

- Encourage organizations to implement mandatory gender sensitivity and bias training for all employees, including management. Such training can help raise awareness about gender-related issues, foster understanding, and promote a more inclusive workplace culture.

- When an incidence occurs for women at workplace that issue should be immediately dealt with and the authorities should take steps immediately, and giving a space to women to open-up and register the complaint without any hesitation.
- Encourage diverse representation in leadership positions and decision-making bodies.
- Engage in public awareness campaigns and advocacy efforts to highlight the importance of gender equality in the workplace.
- Advocate for regular pay audits to identify and rectify gender-based pay disparities.

Conclusion

The data underscores gender distribution in various sectors, notably in teaching and private jobs, underscoring the significance of the education field for female employment. The data also highlights the existence of pervasive gender discrimination in workplaces, necessitating proactive measures to address issues like bias, lost opportunities, and gender-related challenges. Furthermore, it's positive to note that many working women endorse gender equality principles and receive support from their managers; though translating these beliefs into tangible actions for fostering equitable and inclusive work environments remains a crucial challenge.

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